

Design and evaluation of effervescent tablet using butterfly blue pea flower powder

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Abstract:

Butterfly pea (*Clitoria ternatea*) is a medicinal plant known for its high anthocyanin content, antioxidant activity, and vibrant blue pigmentation. This study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of effervescent tablets containing butterfly pea flower powder. Effervescent tablets provide an alternative oral dosage form with increased patient compliance and faster onset of action due to rapid disintegration in water. A direct compression technique was employed using citric acid and sodium bicarbonate as effervescent agents. The formulated tablets were subjected to physicochemical evaluation including weight variation, hardness, friability, moisture content, pH of solution, effervescence time, and in vitro dissolution profile. The results demonstrated that the tablets met all the required pharmacopoeias standards with rapid effervescence and high anthocyanin release, making them suitable as a health supplement.

Keywords: Effervescent tablet, *Clitoria ternatea*, Rapid disintegration, Oral dosage form, Health supplement, Pharmacopoeial evaluation.

INTRODUCTION

Effervescent tablets are a new and patient-friendly dosage form that is well known for its improved bioavailability, simplicity of administration, and quick disintegration. Effervescent tablet, in contrast to traditional solid oral forms, dissolve in water before to intake, providing a practical substitute for populations with swallowing issues, including elderly and paediatric patients. Their effervescence, which usually comes from a mixture of sodium bicarbonate and citric acid, enhances flavour and facilitates quicker absorption of the active components.[1]

The use of natural components in pharmaceutical and nutraceutical formulations has gained popularity in recent years. The butterfly pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*), a bright blue flowering plant indigenous to Southeast Asia, is one of these that has become a multipurpose plant with important therapeutic and nutritional value. Butterfly pea flowers, which have long been utilised in Thai and Ayurvedic medicine, are abundant in bioactive substances such phenolic acids, flavonoids, and anthocyanins (especially ternatins), which have strong anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant, antibacterial, and neuroprotective properties.[2]

Butterfly pea flowers are popular in functional food and beverage items because of its vibrant blue pigment, which is pH-sensitive and changes colour in acidic or alkaline settings. Beyond its visual attractiveness, the plant's health-promoting qualities make it a viable option for the creation of contemporary dosage forms meant to enhance well-being and fend off illnesses linked to oxidative stress.[3]

The development and assessment of effervescent tablets with butterfly pea flower powder as the main active ingredient are the main objectives of this study. The goal is to create an

effervescent dosage form that is stable, pleasant, and functionally successful while preserving the phytochemical advantages of the flower. To find the best formulation, important factors such as effervescence time, pH, disintegration, mechanical strength, and sensory acceptability are evaluated. A combination of contemporary pharmaceutical technology and traditional herbal expertise is represented by the incorporation of butterfly pea flower into an effervescent tablet, providing a natural, health-promoting solution for today's wellness-conscious consumer. [4]

Despite several drawbacks, such as delayed absorption and a longer onset of action, oral dosage forms are the most widely used method of pharmaceutical administration. Although administering the medication in liquid form can get around this, many APIs have a low degree of stability in liquid form. Effervescent tablets serve as a substitute dosage form as a result. Just prior to administration, the tablet is mixed with a glass of water, and the drug solution or dispersion is to be consumed right away. When alkali metal carbonates or bicarbonates interact with tartaric acid and citric acid in the presence of water, the tablet is rapidly broken up by the internal release of CO₂ in the water.

The aim of this study is to highlight the formulation, benefit and application of effervescent tablet made from butterfly pea flower.

- To produce faster onset of action
- To achieve better patient compliance.
- To avoid the First Pass Effect

The properties of the effervescent tablets should be adequate.

- Compared to other dose forms, tablets have a higher bioavailability.
- The effervescent tablets need a controlled environment that is extremely humid. Effervescent tablets can be produced in a typical setting with unmaintained humidity and temperature.
- Tablets have a quicker onset of action and higher patient compliance [5].

Materials and Method

Materials:

- Butterfly pea flower obtained from the local garden
- Butterfly pea flower powder, citric acid, tartaric acid, sodium carbonate, mannitol, talc, microcrystalline cellulose, Magnesium stearate used to manufacture effervescent tablet [6].

Fig no.1 Butterfly pea flower

Ingredient used in effervescent tablet

Ingredient	Amount (g) for 20 tablet
Butterfly pea flower powder	4g
Citric acid	10g
Tartaric acid	2g
Sodium bicarbonate	6g
Talc	0.4g
Microcrystalline cellulose	0.4
Magnesium bicarbonate	0.4

Table no 1. Ingredient used in effervescent tablet

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Preformulation

Step 1: Preparation of Butterfly Pea Flower powder

- Dry Flowers: Used a shade-drying method for the flowers to preserve their bioactive compounds.
- Powder: Grinded dried flowers into a fine powder.

Step 2: Mixing Effervescent Base

- **Dry Mixing:**
- Mixed citric acid, tartaric acid and sodium bicarbonate thoroughly in a dry environment to avoid premature reaction.
- Added a Excipients:
- Added mannitol, talc, and butterfly pea flower powder to the mix.
- Ensured uniform distribution of the flower powder to maintain consistent color and activity.

Step 3: Binding

- Added a small amount of MCC solution (Microcrystalline cellulose)

Step 4: Wet Massing

- The binder solution is slowly added to the dry mix while mixing to form a wet mass with adequate consistency.

Step 5: Granulation (Wet Screening)

- The wet mass is passed through a sieve (14 mesh) to form granules of desired size.

Step 6: Drying

- Spread the granules on a tray and dry in an oven at 40–50°C until moisture content is below 2%. [7,8,9].

Fig no.2 Dried butterfly pea flower powder

Evaluation of granules of butterfly pea flower:

Angle of repose:

The fixed funnel method was used to measure it. In the fixed funnel method, graph paper was set on a level horizontal surface and a funnel was fixed with its tip at a specific height H.

$$\tan(\theta) = \frac{h}{r}$$

Evaluation parameter	F1	F2	F3
Angle of repose	46	43	36

Bulk density:

Used a funnel, a precisely weighed granulation sample was cautiously introduced to the measurement cylinder. The volume was then recorded. The packing's volume was measured using a technique that included a mechanical tapping device and a graded cylinder.[10].

$$BD = \frac{\text{granules weight}}{\text{packing value}}$$

Evaluation parameter	F1	F2	F3
Bulk density	0.80 g/cm ³	0.40 g/cm ³	0.50 g/cm³

Tapped density:

The process described above was adhered to. The last volume was tapped until there was no more audible drop. The following formula is used to calculate the packed bulk density.

$$TD = \frac{\text{granules weight}}{\text{tapped value of the packing}}$$

Evaluation parameter	F1	F2	F3
Tapped density	1.05	0.588	0.625

Carr's index:

Carr's index for butterfly pea flower granules was measured to evaluate the bulk density and tapped density [11].

$$\text{Carr's index} = \frac{[(BD - TD)100]}{TD}$$

Evaluation parameter	F1	F2	F3
Carr's index	23%	20%	19%

POST FORMULATION

PREPARATION OF EFFERVESCENT TABLET BY DIRECT COMPRESSION METHOD [12]

- Preparation of Powder Mixture
Combine effervescent base with butterfly pea flowers (trituated with sweeteners)
- Powder Compression
Compress the powder using rod number 14 in a single punch machine
- Tablet Drying
Dry the compressed tablets in an oven at 60°C for 1 hour
- Packaging
Package the dried tablet

Fig no.3 Preparation of effervescent tablet

Physicochemical Evaluation of the Effervescent Tablets

Weight Variation:

Twenty tablets were chosen at random, weighed separately, and their weights were compared to the mean weight that was determined. [13].

Physicochemical parameter	F1	F2	F3
Weight variation	130mg or less	130mg to 324mg	More than 324mg

Friability Test:

Used a friabilator the tablets' friability was assessed. The tablets were put through a combination of shock and abrasion in a plastic chamber that rotated at 25 rpm for four minutes, dropping a tablet six inches high with each revolution. Weighing the tablets again was done. The tablets were reweighed after being de-dusted with a gentle muslin towel. [14]

$$\frac{\text{initial weight of tablet} - \text{final weight of tablet}}{\text{initial weight of tablet}} \times 100$$

Fig no.4 Friability test apparatus

Physicochemical parameter	F1	F2	F3*
Friability test	1.7%	1.1%	0.8%

Thickness:

It made used of a vernier calliper to ascertain the thickness of ten randomly chosen tablets.

Fig no.5 Vernier calliper

Physicochemical parameter	F1	F2	F3
Thickness test	3.58mm	3.38mm	3.87mm

Hardness test:

The hardness or crushing strength of a tablet is the amount of force needed to break it down in a compression. Ten tablets were chosen at random for this investigation and put one at a time in a hardness tester. The tablet' hardness was then recorded in N.1.

Fig no.6 Hardness tester

Physicochemical parameter	F1	F2	F3
Hardness test	1.7N to 3.4N	1.75N to 3.5N	1.8N to 4.5N

Evaluating the Solution pH:

Three tablets were dissolved in three beakers with 200 ml of water to determine the pH of the solution using a pH meter. [15]

Fig no.7pH Test Apparatus

Physicochemical parameter	F1	F2	F3
pH	5.41	5.82	6.02

Effervescent time:

Stopwatch was used to measure the amount of effervescence that occurred after three tablets were placed in three beakers of water. The time at which a clear solution was obtained was known as the effervescence time One. [16]

Fig no.8 Effervescent tablet in beaker

Disintegration test:

Methodology Pour 900 mL of filtered water at $37 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ into a 1000 mL beaker. Fill the beaker with one effervescent tablet. As soon as possible, begin the stopwatch and watch the disintegration process. When the tablet completely dissolves (within 5 minutes according to USP/BP criteria), the test is finished. Note the period of disintegration. [17].

Physicochemical parameter	F1	F2	F3
Disintegration test	8min	6min	2min

Fig no.9 Disintegration Test Apparatus

In vitro dissolution study:

Dissolution testing was performed using USP Apparatus II (paddle method) at 75 rpm in 900 mL of distilled water maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. Samples were withdrawn at 2, 5, 10, and 15 minutes and analyzed using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer at 595 nm. [18,19]

Fig no.10 Dissolution test apparatus

Dissolution profile :(%Cumulative Release)

Time (min)	Mean absorbance	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Release(vs. 100%standard)
5	0.321	3.1	60%
10	0.562	5.4	74%
15	0.789	7.5	85%
20	0.931	9.0	90%
25	0.990	9.2	92%

Table no.2 Dissolution profile

6. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

The project on the formulation of effervescent tablets using butterfly pea flower powder has demonstrated a successful integration of natural plant-based ingredients into a modern, user-friendly dosage form. The butterfly pea flower, rich in anthocyanins and retained its functional benefits when formulated into effervescent tablets. The final product showed excellent physical characteristics, including rapid disintegration, acceptable hardness, uniform weight, and an appealing natural color. Moreover, the tablets produced a refreshing and stable beverage upon dissolution, aligning with consumer preferences for natural, health-promoting, and convenient supplements.

This formulation presents significant potential for commercial development in the nutraceutical and functional food industries, offering a natural alternative to synthetic products. Future work may include long-term stability studies, bioavailability assessments, and sensory evaluations to further support product optimization and market readiness.

Overall, the study showed that effervescent tablets are a practical and efficient method of delivering butterfly pea flower's health-promoting properties. The formulation is a viable product for the functional food market since it has benefits such as ease of use, quick onset of action, and enhanced taste and aesthetic appeal. This experiment demonstrates how cutting-edge pharmaceutical technology can be combined with traditional herbal. This formulation has the potential to make a substantial contribution to the growing functional food and nutraceutical sectors by fusing traditional botanical knowledge with contemporary medication delivery technologies.

Additionally, this formulation supports the global movement toward plant-based wellness and offers opportunities for innovation in areas such as:

- Functional beverages
- Travel-friendly supplements
- Beauty-from-within products
- pH-sensitive novelty drinks (color-changing for marketing appeal)

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